

MDCT Evaluation of Blunt Renal Trauma**Pallavi Gurumurthy¹, Sadananda Billal², Arun Kumar Basawaraj Modi³, Yashwanth Naik Muddanahalli Balakrishna Naik⁴**¹Senior Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Subbaiah Institute of Medical Science, Shivamogga, Karnataka²Assistant Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Shimoga Institute of Medical College, Shivamogga, Karnataka³Junior Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Mysore Medical College and Research Institute, Karnataka⁴Junior Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Mysore Medical College and Research Institute, Karnataka

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to assess the pattern of injuries in blunt renal trauma using Multiphasic Contrast-Enhanced Computed Tomography (CECT).**Materials and methods:** The study was conducted in the Department of Radio diagnosis, Mysore Medical College and Research Institute.**Results:** Majority were males (80%) with male to female ratio of 4:1. The age of the patients in this study ranged from 6 years to 90 years, with a mean age of 30.4 years. In our study, road traffic accident was the most common mechanism of injury. Grade IV injury was the most common injury. In our study, 4 out of 35 patients had undergone operative management and rest of the patients managed conservatively.**Conclusion:** Renal trauma management has evolved during the last decades, with a clear transition towards a nonoperative approach. This transition is probably because of the improvement in imaging modalities (mainly computed tomography (CT) scanning) and minimally invasive treatment techniques. Thus, a prompt and accurate diagnosis is critical and CECT plays a very important role in characterising the grade of injury and formulate the appropriate management protocols deemed necessary.**Keywords:** American Association for the Surgery of Trauma, Contrast-enhanced computed tomography, renal injury scale.

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Introduction

The kidneys are the most vulnerable genitourinary organ in trauma, as they are involved in up to 5% of trauma patients. [1,2] The most common mechanism for renal injury is blunt trauma (predominantly by motor vehicle accidents and falls), while penetrating trauma (mainly caused by firearms and stab wound) comprise the rest. The mainstay of renal trauma diagnosis is based on contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) and is considered the gold standard method for the radiographic assessment of patients with renal trauma and has completely replaced IVP, which is indicated in all hemodynamically stable patients. [3]

In 80–95 % of the cases renal injuries occur in the setting of blunt trauma, as a result of a direct trauma to the back, flank, lower thorax or upper abdomen or of a rapid deceleration, whereas penetrating traumas are responsible for the

remaining 5–20%. [4-6] renal trauma may occur in isolation or in association with other visceral injuries, with the majority of isolated renal injuries represented by low-grade lesions. [7-9] although gross haematuria is the typical presenting symptom of renal injury, it may be absent in about 5 % of renal injuries, and its presence is not directly correlated with injury severity: for example, haematuria is typically absent in vascular pedicle injuries and ureteral-pelvic injuries. [10,11]

According to the American Association for the Surgery of Trauma (AAST), on the basis of surgical findings renal injuries can be subdivided into five main categories with a progressively poorer prognosis. [12] Contrast enhanced computed tomography (CECT) is the modality of choice for evaluation of renal injuries today and can delineate the various grades of injury and associated complications. Depending upon the imaging

findings, patients may be taken for interventional procedures rather than surgery. [13] With a short examination time, CT provides all the necessary information relating to the degree of parenchymal injury with or without involvement of pelvicalyceal system and renal vascular injuries and also provides information regarding the functional status of the kidneys. Apart from the surgical grading by the American Association, an imaging-based grading system is now the most widely used system to describe renal injuries and carries management and prognostic implications. Renal injuries are classified into grades 1–5 based on the severity of the injury using the American Association for the Surgery of Trauma (AAST) organ injury severity scale. [14]

Objectives:

- To study the pattern of injuries in blunt renal trauma using Multiphasic Contrast-Enhanced Computed Tomography (CECT).
- To classify the grades of the renal injuries among these patients using the American Association for the Surgery of Trauma (AAST) grading system.

Materials and Methods:

- The study was conducted in the Department of Radio diagnosis, Mysore Medical College and Research Institute.
- Sample size: 35
- Type of study: Descriptive study

Inclusion criteria:

1. Positive FAST examination for intraperitoneal or perinephric collection.
2. Clinical suspicion of renal injury following blunt trauma abdomen (gross hematuria).
3. Haemodynamically stable patients.

Exclusion criteria:

1. All haemodynamically unstable patients who would be taken up for surgery immediately were excluded from the study.

Protocol:

- CT was performed using Somatom 128slice dual energy CT scanner (Siemens, Germany).
- CECT was done in four phases: pre-contrast, postcontrast cortimedullary (20 to 30 s post injection), nephrogenic (70-90 s) and delayed (5–10 min) phases. Patients received 1.5 to 2 mL/kg of i.v. contrast media.
- The pre-contrast phase can identify active bleeding or intraparenchymal hematoma. Post-contrast phases identify parenchymal and vascular damage, including the presence of active extravasation of contrast, and other solid organ damage. The delayed phase can visualize the collecting system and possible ureteric injury.

Statistical methods:

Statistical analysis were performed with Epi info version 7. Frequency and proportions were calculated & was depicted using tables, graphs & pie charts.

Results and Discussion:

Table 1: Sex distribution

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	28	80%
Female	7	20%
Total	35	100%

Majority were males (80%) with male to female ratio of 4:1.

Figure 1: Sex distribution

Table 2: Age distribution of patients

Age Group (Years)	Frequency	Percentage
1 To 15	13	37%
16 To 30	8	23%
31 To 50	9	26%
> 50	5	14%
Total	35	100%

The age of the patients in this study ranged from 6 years to 90 years, with a mean age of 30.4 years.

Figure 2: Age Frequency

Table 3: Mode of injury

Mode Of Injury	Frequency	Percentage
RTA	17	49%
Fall	12	34%
Assault	4	11%
Others	2	6%
Total	35	100%

In our study, road traffic accident was the most common mechanism of injury.

Figure 3: Mode of injury

Table 4: AAST Grade of injury

Grade Of Injury	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 1	2	6%
Grade 2	5	14%
Grade 3	8	23%
Grade 4	18	51%
Grade 5	2	6%
Total	35	100%

Grade IV injury was the most common injury.

Table 5: Management and outcome of patients

Management	No. Of Patients	Percentage
Conservative	31	89%
Operative	4	11%
Total	35	100%

Figure 4: Management

In our study, 4 out of 35 patients had undergone operative management and rest of the patients managed conservatively.

AAST Grading and CT Findings:

The most common renal trauma classification followed is the American Association for the

Surgery of Trauma (AAST) classification (Table 1), scaled from 1 to 5, representing the least to the most severe injury. The AAST grade is a predictor for morbidity and mortality in blunt and penetrating renal injury. The AAST grade has a statistically significant correlation with the need for surgery and for the risk for nephrectomy.

Table 6: Renal Injury Scoring Scale by the American Association for the Surgery of Trauma (AAST)

Grade*	Type of injury	Description of injury
I	Contusion	Microscopic or gross hematuria, urologic studies normal
	Hematoma	Subcapsular, nonexpanding without parenchymal laceration
II	Hematoma	Nonexpanding perirenal hematoma confirmed to renal retroperitoneum
	Laceration	<1.0 cm parenchymal depth of renal cortex without urinary extravasation
III	Laceration	>1.0 cm parenchymal depth of renal cortex without collecting system rupture or urinary extravasation
	Laceration	Parenchymal laceration extending through renal cortex, medulla, and collecting system
IV	Vascular	Main renal artery or vein injury with contained hemorrhage
V	Laceration	Completely shattered kidney
	Vascular	Avulsion of renal hilum which devascularizes kidney

Figure 5: Illustration of Subcapsular hematoma

Figure 6: Subcapsular hematoma (grade I) in a 30-year-old male who had sustained blunt abdominal trauma. Contrast-enhanced CT scan demonstrates a subcapsular fluid collection (white arrow) flattening the posterolateral contour of the left kidney

Figure 7: Drawing illustrates a focal intrarenal hematoma/ contusion

Figure 8: Axial CECT demonstrating a contusion (black arrow) in the left kidney as a focal relatively hypo attenuating region with indistinct margin. A renal contusion is classified as an AAST grade 1 injury

Figure 9: Illustration of a small cortical laceration with adjacent perirenal hematoma limited by Gerota's fascia

Figure 10: Axial CECT in a 28 year-old female with penetrating abdominal trauma, showing a laceration less than 1 cm involving interpole region of the left kidney (white arrow) with subcapsular hematoma. This laceration clearly does not extend to a calyx or pelvis, hence this injury would be classified as AAST grade 2

Figure 11: Illustration of a laceration that extends to the medulla but does not involve the collecting system

Figure 12: 75 year-old male with AAST grade 3 renal injury. Lacerations involving interpole and lower pole of left kidney not extending into collecting system (no evidence of urine extravasation) with perinephric hematoma. There was normal contrast opacification of renal vessels (not shown).

Figure 13: Illustration of deep parenchymal lacerations involving the collecting system

Figure 14: Drawing illustrates a subsegmental infarct

Figure 15: Subsegmental renal infarction in a young male who had sustained blunt abdominal trauma. Contrast-enhanced CT scan in portal venous (A) and excretory phases (B) demonstrates a sharply demarcated, wedge-shaped non-enhancing area in the lower pole region of the right kidney (white arrow). Note also the evidence of perinephric hematoma. The patient also had liver lacerations.

Figure 16: Drawing illustrates thrombosis of the main renal artery.

Figure 17: Traumatic occlusion of the right main renal artery (grade IV) in a 38-year-old man who had sustained blunt abdominal trauma. Contrast-enhanced CT scan demonstrates a diminished right nephrogram with no active contrast extravasation. Fig. B shows filling defect in right main renal artery (white arrow)

Figure 18: Illustration of shattered kidney with vascular pedicle injury

Figure 19: Urinary extravasation from renal collecting system injury. Coronal CECT of a 24 year-old male in portal venous/nephrographic phase (A) and excretory phase (B), showing a linear through and through laceration disrupting the right renal parenchyma, calyceal system with urinary extravasation. In (B), excreted contrast leaks out of the collecting system and accumulates along the inferior aspect of the kidney (arrow)-s/o grade V injury. Urinary collecting system involvement is a feature of only AAST grade 4 or 5 injury.

Discussion

Severe renal injuries are usually associated with multisystem injuries, may require interventional radiology to control hemorrhage and improve the chances for renal salvage, if there is significant perinephric fluid, especially medially, or deep laceration, delayed images should be obtained to evaluate for urinary extravasation. The presence of urinary extravasation and large devitalized areas of renal parenchyma, especially with associated injuries of intraperitoneal organs, is particularly prone to complication and usually requires surgery. Active hemorrhage should be recognized because it often indicates a need for urgent surgery or embolization to prevent exsanguination. [15] Generally accepted indications for kidney trauma imaging are: penetrating injury and hematuria, blunt trauma and gross hematuria, microscopic hematuria and hypotension, microscopic hematuria and significant associated injuries, direct contusion or hematoma of flank soft tissue, fractures of the lower ribs, transverse processes or dorso-lumbar spine. [16] CT has replaced intravenous urography and became the diagnostic tool of choice for the assessment of renal trauma and other associated injuries. [17] Majority were males (80%) with male to female ratio of 4:1. The age of the patients in this study ranged from 6 years to 90 years, with a mean age of 30.4 years.

In our study, road traffic accident was the most common mechanism of injury. Grade IV injury was the most common injury. In our study, 4 out of 35 patients had undergone operative management and rest of the patients managed conservatively. CT provides all the necessary information relating to the degree of parenchymal injury with or without involvement of pelvi calyceal system and renal vascular injuries and also provides information regarding the functional status of the kidneys. Doing a phasic scan also helps in differentiating active hemorrhage from urine extravasation. [18] With the wider availability of newer CT machines and helical multislice scanners, much faster scanning, increased volume coverage and improved multiplanar reconstruction ability now can provide high quality images with shorter time on the table for the patient. [19] As most of the patients undergoing CT scan are not so co-operative in breath holding, motion artifacts can frequently compromise the study and lead to added confusion in interpreting the scan. Faster imaging with multislice scanner and multiplanar reconstruction can help to overcome these problems and provide an accurate assessment of injury. [20] MDCT scanning is the only imaging modality that can provide information required to grade renal injuries as part of the AAST renal injury grading system. [21]

Management Options:

Renal trauma management has evolved during the last decades, with a clear transition toward a nonoperative approach. This transition is probably because of the improvement in imaging modalities [mainly computed tomography (CT) scanning] and in minimally invasive treatment techniques. The lion's share of renal trauma patients are managed nonoperatively with careful monitoring, reimaging when there is any deterioration, and the use of minimally invasive procedures. These procedures include angioembolization in cases of active bleeding and endourological stenting in cases of urine extravasation.

Conclusion:

Renal trauma management has evolved during the last decades, with a clear transition towards a nonoperative approach. This transition is probably because of the improvement in imaging modalities (mainly computed tomography (CT) scanning) and minimally invasive treatment techniques. Thus, a prompt and accurate diagnosis is critical and CECT plays a very important role in characterising the grade of injury and formulate the appropriate management protocols deemed necessary.

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